

Questionnaire on AI Tools, Language Proficiency, Autonomy, Critical Thinking, and Ethics (AI-LPAC-E)

This questionnaire (AI-LPAC-E) was designed by Vahid Ghorbani (2025) to investigate the relationship between AI tools, English language proficiency, learner autonomy, critical thinking, and ethical concerns. It includes demographic items, Likert-scale statements adapted from validated sources, and open-ended questions. The instrument aims to provide insights into the perceived impact of AI-assisted language learning.

Section A: Demographics & AI Usage

1. Age
2. Gender: Male / Female / Other
3. Education level: BA / MA / PhD
4. Years of English study
5. Self-rated proficiency (CEFR): A1–C2
6. AI tools used: ChatGPT / Grammarly / Other
7. Frequency of use: Daily / Weekly / Monthly / Rarely
8. Main purpose: Writing / Speaking / Vocabulary / Grammar / Translation

Section B: Perceived Impact on Language Proficiency (12 items): (Adapted from Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Johnson & Smith, 2019)

9. AI tools help me identify and correct grammatical mistakes in my writing.
10. Using AI has improved my awareness of English grammar rules.
11. I rely on AI suggestions to check the grammatical accuracy of my work.
12. AI tools expand my vocabulary knowledge.
13. AI helps me choose more accurate or academic words.
14. AI feedback increases my ability to use collocations correctly.
15. AI tools help me organize my writing more clearly.
16. AI feedback improves my sentence structure.
17. I feel more confident in writing assignments with AI support.
18. Chatbots improve my confidence in speaking English.
19. AI speaking tasks help me practice pronunciation.

20. Using AI tools reduces my speaking anxiety.

Section C: Learner Autonomy (8 items): (Orakci, 2017; Van Nguyen & Habók, 2021)

21. I set personal goals for my English learning.

22. I choose my own strategies when learning English.

23. I monitor my progress without relying solely on teachers.

24. I decide which resources to use for practice.

25. I take responsibility for correcting my mistakes.

26. I am able to study English independently without constant teacher support.

27. I manage my learning time effectively.

28. I adapt my learning strategies when I face difficulties.

Section D: Critical Thinking (8 items): (Tsui et al., 2021)

29. When I get an AI answer, I check other sources to confirm it.

30. I analyze AI feedback critically before accepting it.

31. I usually accept AI suggestions without much questioning. (Reverse-scored)

32. AI tools encourage me to reflect on different perspectives.

33. I can detect when AI feedback is inconsistent.

34. I question the reliability of AI-generated references.

35. I evaluate whether AI-generated information is logical.

36. I compare AI outputs with my own reasoning.

Section E: Ethical Concerns & Academic Integrity (8 items): (Mavrinac et al., 2010; Williamson, 2017; O'Neil, 2016)

37. Using AI for assignments without acknowledgment is a form of plagiarism.

38. I worry about the privacy of my personal data when using AI tools.

39. AI systems may show cultural or linguistic bias.

40. I am concerned that overreliance on AI may reduce my originality.

41. Teachers should provide clear guidelines for ethical AI use.

42. It is acceptable to use AI-generated texts without citation. (Reverse-scored)

- 43. AI-based learning may undermine fairness in academic work.
- 44. AI feedback may sometimes mislead students into plagiarism unintentionally.

Section F: Attitudes Toward Technology in Learning (6 items): (Davis, 1989; Teo, 2010)

- 45. Using AI makes learning English easier for me.
- 46. AI tools make learning more enjoyable.
- 47. AI is a valuable supplement to traditional instruction.
- 48. Relying on AI may weaken human interaction in the classroom. (Reverse-scored)
- 49. I believe AI will play an important role in the future of education.
- 50. AI saves me time and effort in language learning tasks.

Open-Ended Questions

- 51. What is the biggest benefit you experienced when using AI for English learning?
- 52. What is the biggest risk or problem you see with AI in your learning?

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